

Deliverable D7.7.

COMMUNICATIONS WITH POLICY MAKERS PLAN

Deliverable report

Deliverable No.	D7.7	Work Package No.	WP7	Task/s No.	Tasks 7.4
Work Package Title	MECHANISMS FOR SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE & INTERACTION WITH THE POLICY MAKERS				
Linked Task/s Title	Requirements for Communication with policy makers & public bodies.				
Status		Final			
Dissemination level	PU	PU-Public			
Due date deliverable	2023-01-31	Submission date	2023-01-31		
Deliverable version	DEQ_D7.7_ANE_V1.1_20221226.doc				

Document Contributors

Deliverable responsible	ANEFA	
Contributors	Organisation	
CÉSAR LUACES FRADES	ANEFA	
LORENA VILADÉS SANTOS	ANEFA	
PAULO ROMERO MARTÍNEZ	ANEFA	
Reviewers	Organisation	
LUCIA EGUILLOR	ZABALA	
MAYELA GRAVALOS	APP CONSULTORÍA	
ELISA ISOTAHDON	METSO OUTOTEC	

Document History

Version	Date	Comment
1.0	2022-06-01	First version
1.1	2022-12-26	Second version

Disclaimer

This document reflects only the author's view. Responsibility for the information and views expressed therein lies entirely with the authors. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Table of contents

Deliverable report.....	3
Document Contributors	3
Document History	3
Disclaimer	4
Table of contents	5
List of Abbreviations	7
1 Executive Summary.....	8
2 Introduction	9
2.1 The DiGIECOQUARRY project.....	9
2.2 Scope of the deliverable	10
2.3 Feeding RMIS and EURMKB	11
2.4 Procedures for communication with policy makers.....	11
2.5 Relation to other activities and deliverables.....	11
2.6 Structure of the deliverable	13
3 Communications with policy makers plan	14
3.1 General approach	14
3.2 Plan for the periodic and recurrent communications with policy makers	16
3.2.1 Identification of policy makers, regulators and public bodies, and creation of database	16
3.2.2 Communication materials to be used	16
3.2.3 Timing	17
3.2.4 Submitting information.....	17
3.3 Plan for the specific communications according to needs of the project	18
3.4 Plan for the close interaction between DIGIECOQUARRY and the policy makers and public bodies.....	19
3.4.1 Participation in enquiries and surveys	19
3.4.2 Meetings and policy briefings	19
3.4.3 Invitation to policy makers and public bodies.....	20
4 KPIs	22
4.1 Evidence.....	22
4.2 KPIs	22
5 Management control timetable.....	24
6 Conclusions	25

7	References	26
8	Annex I. Consortium Members preassigned to policy makers	27
9	Annex II. Consortium Members preassigned to the International Advisory Board	32
10	Annex III. Consortium Members preassigned to organisations supporting DIGIECOQUARRY	34
11	Annex IV. Format of the management control timetable	35

List of Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	DESCRIPTION
D	Deliverable
DEQ	DIGIECOQUARRY
IQS	Intelligent Quarrying System
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PM	Policy maker
PC	Project Coordinator
CM	Consortium Members
WP	Work Package
WP Leader	Work Package Leader
CHAL	Chalmers University of Technology,
UPM-AI	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid – Artificial Intelligence
DGA	Dirección General de Asturias
FAEN	Fundación Asturiana de la Energía
ASO	Asogravas
MIN	Mintek
ZAB	Zabala Innovation Consulting
MUL	Montanuniversität Leoben
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisation
DGs	Development Goals
SLO	Social License to Operate
EURMKB	European Union Raw Materials Knowledge Base
IAB	International Advisory Board
RMIS	Raw Materials Information System

1 Executive Summary

This document describes the plan for the communication with policy makers and public bodies of DIGIECOQUARRY (DEQ). It defines the work procedure to meet the project's goals set for this topic.

This deliverable is directly related to ***D7.6 Requirements for communication with policy makers and public bodies***. Both documents must be used together by all Consortium Members to ensure the correct execution of the plan and the fulfilment of the objectives. The results of this plan will be showcased in months 36 and 48 in ***D7.8*** and ***D7.9 Evaluation report for communications with policy makers***.

Here are included the structure of the deliverable as well as its scope, its relation to other tasks, activities and deliverables, and the procedures and plans to follow.

The different goals of the communication with policy makers and public bodies are stated in ***D7.6 Requirements for communication with policy makers and public bodies***.

The deliverable defines more precisely than D7.6 the partners' requirements and roles in the communication plan according to the different categories of policy makers, regulators and public bodies at international, EU, national, regional, and local levels.

The reference to dissemination and communication materials and tools is made to WP9 materials.

The deliverable describes the timeline of the plan, as well as the type of evidence and KPI to guarantee proper monitoring.

2 Introduction

2.1 The DIGIECOQUARRY project

DIGIECOQUARRY is a Horizon 2020 project aiming to design, develop and validate in 5 pilot environments an Innovative Quarrying System (IQS) comprising sensors, processes, tools and methods for data capture, processing and sharing to provide integrated, digitalised, automatic, and real-time process control for aggregates quarries.

The DEQ consortium will combine the latest researched and advanced technologies applied to quarry operation together with the integration of selected innovative digital solutions to boost the capacity of the aggregates industry, enhance health and safety conditions for workers, improve the process and efficiency of the aggregates extractive sites, maximise sustainability and resource efficiency in the quarry operations, and foster social acceptance.

Figure 1. DIGIECOQUARRY's concept.

2.2 Scope of the deliverable

This report, titled *D7.7 Communications with policy makers plan*, aims to determine the strategy and procedures, including the actions and activities to be implemented along the project, for communication and interaction with public policies to maximise the project's visibility and impact.

This deliverable has been developed under WP7 Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policy makers, aiming to define and implement one-way and two-way interactions with policy makers.

Task 7.4 Requirements for communication with policy makers & public bodies is led by ANEFA and the partners involved are MUL, CHAL, UPM-AI, DGA, FAEN, ASO, MIN, and ZAB. This task will define fair & transparent communication requirements in line with WP9.

Task 7.4 is subdivided in:

- **ST7.4.1. Definition of legal requirements applicable to aggregates quarries.** Due to the complexity of dealing with regional and national specificities, European requirements will be taken as a reference. The national, regional, and local requirements will only be considered for each pilot site. The IQS platform will have the possibility to establish particular threshold values for each site as a reference for the indicators delivered by the system.
- **ST7.4.2. Actions and proposals for a sustainable management of environment protection, climate change prevention and ecological transition.** Also, actions and proposals to optimise the management of the production process, to increase efficiency and productivity, including health and safety and social acceptance. In terms of the process, each one of the phases will be analysed to propose specific tools for its improvement.
- **ST7.4.3. Definition of indicators, trends, and levels to be achieved in each one, covering the following criteria** (1) Ensuring supply to meet the demand for the product in a near, medium or distant environment; (2) Efficient use of natural resources; (3) Application of measures to promote and improve the health and safety conditions for the workers; (4) Contribution to the economic development of the community; (5) Contribution to the social development of the community; (6) of the affected natural space; (7) Application of the best techniques available in integrated pollution prevention and control and waste management.

This Task is also linked with:

- **T7.5 Interaction with local, national, and international policy makers**, that addresses the implementation and follow-up of the requirements defined in T7.4 in line with the Communication strategy. To that end, a specific plan will be delivered to reach policy makers and other relevant public bodies, or stakeholders related to the aggregates sector. This plan will be tackled at local and national levels (partners' countries) but also EU level and beyond, counting with relevant partners in South Africa and Colombia to achieve worldwide influence.
- **T7.3 Obtention of the Social License to Operate (SLO)**, to foster social acceptance of the quarrying sector by introducing novel participatory processes and engagement actions with local communities and policy makers to obtain and preserve the Social License to Operate (SLO) and improve public acceptance and trust on the new quarrying technologies.

In that sense, solid guidelines to communicate with policy makers and public bodies have been delivered in *D7.6*.

2.3 Feeding RMIS and EURMKB

Close cooperation with policy makers to feed RMIS and EURMKB is being carried out within WP8, together with networking and clustering activities.

2.4 Procedures for communication with policy makers

Communication activities with policy makers and public bodies will be performed through periodical video conferences, webinars, and face-to-face meetings in workshops, conferences, or seminars. On the other hand, social media such as LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram, and YouTube could be used for communication. Working groups with other Mining DGs, mining engineers associations, and experts' groups will be also built during the project to work in different specialisations.

2.5 Relation to other activities and deliverables

Communication with policy makers and public bodies is being developed in close contact and coordination with the other tasks of WP7 and also together with WP8 and WP9 (see Figure 2) because the topics of these WPs are strongly linked.

Figure 2. Relationship between WPs.

The communication with policy makers plan has a very close relationship with the following deliverables:

WP6

- D6.6 Overall assessment of results achieved and KPI analysis.

WP7

- D7.1 Context narrative, social risk matrix and stakeholder mapping.
- D7.2 Social risk analysis.
- D7.3 Communications and social awareness plan.
- D7.4 Community engagement strategy.
- D7.5 Social license to operate.
- **D7.6 Requirements for Communication with policy makers and public bodies (main deliverable linked with this D7.7).**

To avoid constant repetition of topics already delivered in *D.7.6 Requirements for Communication with policy makers and public bodies*, here are summarised the main clauses applicable to this *D7.7*.

The **main objectives** of the communication with policy makers and public bodies are delivered in *D7.6 clause 3*.

As stated in **D7.6** clause 4.1, DIGIECOQUARRY partners do not need a particular set of skills to participate in the project's strategy for communication with policy makers and public bodies.

- **D7.6 clause 4.2** defines the role of each partner in the communication with policy makers and public bodies plan.
- **D7.6 clause 4.3** identifies the Consortium members that are registered in the EU Transparency Register. This is a very relevant asset for the whole communication with policy makers and public bodies plan implementation.
- **D7.6 clause 4.4** lists the members invited to the International Advisory Board – IAB, their added value for the project, their link with other policy makers and public bodies and the partner in charge of the collaboration and connection with them. This is an open list and has been growing with new members. (see new list in Annex II).
- **D7.6 clause 4.5** lists the organisations that explicitly support the project, being them policy makers or public bodies that are key actors for interacting with other organisms. This list is open and is growing with new supporting organisations (see new list in Annex III).
- **D7.6 clause 5.1** maps the policy makers, regulators and public bodies related to the industry that could be interesting to collaborate with to achieve the project objectives. They are listed by type and geographic area (International, EU, National, Regional and Local).
- **D7.6 clause 5.2** proposes expected communication topics related to each policy maker, regulator and public body profile.
- **D7.6 clause 6** explains the dissemination and communication materials and tools and the requirements to deliver them to achieve the objectives.
- **D7.6 clause 7** defines the ethical requirements for communication, including the context, governance, organisation, and structure within DIGIECOQUARRY. It states the legal background and further regulation, the general ethical principles in the DEQ Grant Agreement, the need to always comply with the rules of the EU Transparency Register and its Code of Conduct and, finally, other complementary ethical principles to be applied.
- **D7.6 clauses 8 and 9** respectively define the better regulation requirements and the specific political and regulatory framework for communication.

WP8

- D8.1 Clustering plan.
- D8.2 Protocols to cooperate with RMIS and EURMKB.
- D8.3 and D8.4 Report on interactions with other organisations, projects and the IAB.

WP9

- D9.1 Dissemination, communication, and exploitation plan.
- D9.2 DIGIECOQUARRY's website.
- D9.3 and D9.5 and D9.8 Dissemination and communication materials.
- D9.4 DEQ Communication and dissemination activities report.

WP10

- D10.3 and 10.7 and 10.9 Risk management and contingency plan.

2.6 Structure of the deliverable

With the above in mind, this *D.7.7 Communications with policy makers plan* is structured as follows:

Section 1 – Executive summary.

Section 2 – Introduction. Provides meaningful information regarding the requirements for communication with policy makers and public bodies; it includes the structure of the deliverable as well as its scope, its relation to other tasks, activities, and deliverables and the first description of the procedures for communication with policy makers.

Section 3 – Communications with policy makers plan. Explains the general approach and defines three main groups of actions: 1) periodic and recurrent communications including recommendations about how to identify makers, regulators and public bodies, the creation of a database, the communication materials to be used, the timing of actions, and the procedure to submit information; 2) specific communications according to needs of the project; close interaction related actions like the participation in enquiries and surveys, meetings and policy briefings and invitation to events as speakers or attendant.

Section 4 – KPIs. Defines the evidence to be able to measure and the main KPIs to measure and evaluate the progress.

Section 5 – Timetable. Explains the table to manage, organise and prioritise the communications.

Section 6 – Conclusions. Summarises the conclusions of this deliverable.

Section 7 – References. Includes the main references used for this document.

The **Annexes** include:

- CM preassigned to policy makers.
- CM preassigned to the International Advisory Board.
- CM preassigned to organisations supporting DEQ.
- Format of the management control timetable

3 Communications with policy makers plan

3.1 General approach

The main objective of the communications with policy makers plan is to make it possible to achieve the general objectives of the DEQ project.

The relationship between the project objectives and those of the communication with policy makers and public bodies are expressed in **D7.6 clause 3**.

DEQ has 25 partners, with several linked third parties, from 10 countries (2 of them non-EU) and there are a vast number of policy makers, regulators and public bodies of interest for the project in each of the 27 EU countries involved at national, regional and local level, in addition to European and international bodies. Therefore, it is easy to understand the complexity of managing, implementing, recording, monitoring and evaluating such communication.

Table 1 presents the main categories of policy makers to be integrated into this plan and the partners responsible for doing such.

Policy makers and public bodies	International	EU	National	Regional	Local
Parliament and other legislative and representative bodies	ANEFA with the collaboration of UPM-AI				
Public administrations and governments					
Academia and research stakeholders					
Technological centres					
Standardisation bodies					
Entrepreneurs' organisations					
Corporate aggregates companies					
Technology developers and providers					
Machinery suppliers					
Associations of the construction sector and other clients of the aggregates industry					
Citizens and civil society in general					
Citizens and civil society close to the aggregates sites					
Trade Unions					
Environmental NGOs and Networks					
Thinktanks, other lobbyist entities					
International governance organisations					
Media, journalists, and other groups general					
Media, journalists, and other groups technical					

Table 1. Main categories of policy makers to be integrated in this plan.

This is further complicated by the fact that the project is conducted in English and communication materials are produced in English, whereas in national, regional, and local interactions, the local language will be, in each case, the language of reference.

Moreover, the different members of the Consortium have very different structures and sizes, on the one hand, and very different capacities and possibilities to interact with policy makers, on the other. For this reason, it is very difficult to establish general rules.

Nevertheless, as simplified plan as possible has been prepared. On the one hand, it ensures the fulfilment of the objectives and serves as a reference for all CM. On the other hand, it avoids falling into unproductive bureaucracy that diverts the participants' resources away from the project's objectives.

Annex I establishes, a priori, the CM who are considered best placed to communicate with policy makers, while those preassigned to the members of the International Advisory Board are included in Annex II, and those for organisations supporting DEQ are in Annex III.

As pragmatically as possible, three main types of communication actions have been distinguished:

- Periodic and recurrent communication.
- Specific communication according to the needs of the project.
- Interaction between DEQ and the policy makers and public bodies.

Table 2 presents the objectives of the three defined types of communication.

Type of communication	Objective
Periodic and recurrent communication	Raise awareness on the aggregates industry
	Dissemination of project materials
	Delivery of information about the project - Existence of the project and objectives
	Delivery of information about the project - Developments and preliminary results
	Delivery of information about the project - Final results and conclusions
Specific communication according to needs	Contribution to law-making and the improvement of legislation
	Contribution to new policies, initiatives, and roadmaps for Raw Materials
	Alignment of public policies with emerging innovative mining systems
	Connection with other EU / national initiatives, projects, platforms, and networks
	International cooperation
	Solution of barriers/obstacles
	Reporting on identified opportunities
	Contribution to standardisation
	Contribution to regulatory compliance
	Interaction between scale experimentation and policy making
	Need of use of EU dissemination channels
Other	
Interaction between DEQ and the policy makers and public bodies	Participation in enquiries and surveys
	Meetings and policy briefings
	Invitation to participate in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ DIGIECOQUARRY’s Workshops, seminars and panel presentations ▪ DIGIECOQUARRY ’s final conference ▪ Scientific conferences ▪ Other events, trade fairs and workshops (exhibitions, business events, information days, technical committees, assemblies, etc.).

Table 2. Objectives of the defined types of communication.

Figure 3. Main types of communication with policy makers.

3.2 Plan for the periodic and recurrent communications with policy makers

It is essential to broadcast DEQ to the relevant policy makers, regulators and public bodies with the aim of:

- Raise awareness on the aggregates industry.
- Disseminate project outcomes and materials.
- Deliver information about the project – Its existence and objectives.
- Deliver information about the project – Developments and preliminary results.
- Deliver information about the project – Final results and conclusions.

3.2.1 Identification of policy makers, regulators and public bodies, and creation of a database

It is essential for the successful implementation of the communication plan that each member of the consortium:

a) **Identifies** those policy makers, regulators and public bodies at national, regional, and local levels who are relevant to the project and who, at the same time, can be contacted via email. These should include members of parliament and other legislative and representative bodies, members of public administrations and governments, academia and research actors, technology centres, standardisation bodies, business organisations, aggregates companies, technology developers and suppliers, machinery suppliers, construction sector associations and other aggregates industry clients, citizens and civil society in general, citizens and civil society close to aggregates sites, trade unions, NGOs and environmental networks, thinktanks, other lobbying entities, and journalists from mainstream media.

b) **Creates a simple database** with the following fields: Name and surname of the person, Position or role, Name of the organisation and e-mail address.

3.2.2 Communication materials to be used

To keep it as simple as possible, all dissemination and communication must be based on the materials produced along the development of the project as described in *D9.1 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan*, *D9.2 DIGIECOQUARRY's website*, and *D9.3 and D9.4 and D9.5 Dissemination and Communication materials*.

Among these outputs are signage such as leaflets, brochures and posters and written texts such as press releases, online newsletters, articles in journals and magazines, scientific publications, public deliverables, letters, specific reports, or executive summaries.

The difference between communicating the project to policy makers instead of a general audience will be that ANEFA, as project coordinator, in close collaboration with ZAB and UPM-AI, WP7 and WP8 leaders, will select the relevant information to avoid saturating policy makers with an excessive flow of data.

The objective is to send little but relevant information to arouse the interest and attention of the listeners instead of saturating the communication channel and making the action unproductive.

3.2.3 Timing

The periodic and recurrent communication with policy makers will take place when the supporting information is available and on the joint decision taken by ANEFA as project coordinator in close collaboration with WP7 and WP8 leaders, ZAB and UPM-AI.

3.2.4 Submitting information

3.2.4.1 International and European policy makers, regulators and public bodies

As project coordinator, ANEFA will directly send, on behalf of the CM, the selected information to all International and European policy makers, regulators and public bodies that have been identified as relevant for the project.

If a follow-up is required, ANEFA will be in charge of it.

Figure 4. Relationship between WPs.

3.2.4.2 National, regional and local policy makers, regulators and public bodies

At the same time, ANEFA, as PC, will circulate the selected information to all CM asking them to send it to their own national, regional and local policy makers, regulators and public bodies that they have identified as relevant for the project.

Figure 5. Relationship between WPs.

In the event of several CM located in the same country¹, one of the following options must be chosen:

- To unify the policy makers' databases to create a single one. They must decide who will be responsible for sending the information to the receivers when delivered from ANEFA. In addition, they will have to send the resulting database to ANEFA, as coordinator, for follow-up.
- To maintain each policy maker's databases separately and send the information individually. In addition, they will have to submit their particular database to ANEFA, as coordinators, for follow-up. In this case, some policy makers may receive duplicated information.

If a follow-up is required, each CM will oversee it.

3.3 Plan for the specific communications according to needs of the project

This second case is much more specific than the first one.

The **need to communicate** will appear because of the evolution of the project and could be related to one or more of the below listed reasons:

- Contribution to law-making and the improvement of legislation.
- Contribution to new policies, initiatives, and roadmaps for Raw Materials.
- Alignment of public policies with emerging innovative mining systems.
- Connection with other EU/national initiatives, projects, platforms, and networks.
- International cooperation.
- Solution of barriers/obstacles.
- Reporting on identified opportunities.
- Contribution to standardisation.
- Contribution to regulatory compliance.
- Interaction between scale experimentation and policy making.
- Need of use of EU dissemination channels.
- Other.

These can be identified by one or more of the CM during the project development. It should be remembered that offering proposals and solutions to the European Commission is part of what is proposed to be done within the project.

In the event of any of these, the Consortium Member who has detected it will bring it to the attention of the related Task Leader and WP Leader.

¹ Spain (ANEFA, Hanson, Maxam, UPM-AI, UPM-MIN, Arco, APP, SIGMA, DG Astur, Zabala); Germany (DHP, CSI, ITK); France (Vicat, Akka); Italy (Holcim, ma-estro); Finland (Sandvik, Metso:Outotec); Sweden (Roctim, Chalmers).

In the framework of the WP concerned, the matter will be shaped and reported to the ANEFA coordination team, which will collaborate to definitively formulate the case and identify the policy maker(s) involved. These may be international, EU, national, regional and/or local.

Once the issue is appropriately formulated (as a consultation, proposal, request, contribution, report, etc.) it will be sent by ANEFA as project coordinator on behalf of the Consortium to the relevant policy maker(s). If necessary, it would be accompanied by a meeting request.

ANEFA will be the one making the follow-up. If the communication is at a national, regional, or local level, the collaboration of the WP Leaders and a CM of this country will be requested.

3.4 Plan for the close interaction between DIGIECOQUARRY and the policy makers and public bodies

It is key for the success of DEQ to interact with policy makers and public bodies by means of enquiries and surveys, policy briefings, meetings, and participation in events and conferences.

3.4.1 Participation in enquiries and surveys

When, in a Task, an enquiry or a survey for policy makers and public bodies is foreseen and/or needed, the Task Leader will inform both WP Leader and ANEFA as coordinator. They will evaluate if the collaboration of other partners is required and, if this is the case, they will be invited to join.

The following points must be agreed together:

- Enquiry or survey final content.
- Reply methodology and format. It could be completed online, in a written format, during a meeting, in a Focus group, etc.
- Spokesperson.
- Launch date and calendar.
- Follow-up responsible(s).
- Other.

After the end of the enquiry or the survey, the partner that is the technical responsible for it will deliver to ANEFA a short report on the participation of the policy makers and public bodies.

3.4.2 Meetings and policy briefings

When, in a Task, a meeting or a policy briefing with policy makers (Administrations, political parties, relevant related organisations like entrepreneur organisations, Trade Unions, Accademia, Technological Centres, NGOs, etc.) and public bodies, at EU, national, regional, local and international levels, is foreseen and/or needed to explain DEQ and to discuss potential issues and difficulties identified that could require political actions (policy, legislation, or other) the CM will directly proceed.

The meetings will be organised, as appropriate, in face-to-face, online or hybrid modes, or even with visits to some of the pilot sites.

If an involved CM needs some support or information, it will be free to ask for it to the related Task Leader and/or WP Leader and/or ANEFA as coordinator. ANEFA and WP8 Leader (UPM-AI) will closely collaborate to coordinate the messages to provide an aligned proposal.

If any kind of marketing material is needed, ANEFA will be asked to provide it.

Whenever a relevant meeting or policy briefing to the project takes place, after giving feedback to the Task Leader and/or WP Leader, ANEFA must always be notified as coordinator. Besides, if there are records (programme and/or agenda and/or minutes and/or signature list and/or pictures and/or video, etc.), the Consortium Member participating will send the available information to ANEFA.

3.4.3 Invitation to policy makers and public bodies

In the work programme of DEQ, several workshops, seminars, panel presentations and a final conference are scheduled. During the four years of lifespan of the project, it is foreseen to participate and organise scientific conferences, events, trade fairs, exhibitions, business events, information days, technical committees, assemblies, etc.

It would be of high value for the project to invite selected and appropriate policy makers and public bodies to these events:

- DIGIECOQUARRY's Workshops, seminars and panel presentations.
- DIGIECOQUARRY 's final conference.
- Scientific conferences.
- Other events, trade fairs and workshops (exhibitions, business events, information days, technical committees, assemblies, etc.).

3.4.3.1 Invitation to DIGIECOQUARRY's Workshops, seminars, panel presentations and final conference

ANEFA in cooperation with WP8 Leader (UPM-AI) will coordinate all the Workshops, seminars, panel presentations and the final conference of DEQ as foreseen in **D9.1 Dissemination, communication, and exploitation plan** - Annex XIV:

- 2 workshops in the Spanish Aggregates Congress (2022 and 2025).
- 1 workshop in the ANEFA Chair in Aggregate Technology (Madrid – Spain).
- 1 workshop in the European Network for Sustainable Quarrying and Mining (Brussels - EU).
- 1 Global Innovation and Technology Conference in the RM sector (location to be decided).
- 1 sector and a new Expert Forum: Digitalisation in the RM sector (location to be decided).
- 8 panel presentations in different UEPG Committee Meetings, for panel discussion (locations to be decided).
- 2 panel presentations in the UEPG Entrepreneurs Forum where all the representatives of EU national member associations attend (locations to be decided).
- 2 seminars and panel discussions and networking meetings with 15 to 20 countries represented (Video meetings).

- Local workshops and engagement actions will be organised in the pilot sites to introduce the project to local communities and consider their concerns and fears about its impact.

Once the Consortium decides on the date and venue, the participation of policy makers and public bodies both as speakers and attendees will be agreed upon.

ANEFA will coordinate the above-mentioned invitation and may request the collaboration of other partners who, either because they belong to the country where the event is held, or because of their better access to the organism, may facilitate their involvement.

ANEFA will make a follow-up of the invitations. If the communication is at national, regional, or local level, the WPL and a Consortium Member of that country will collaborate with ANEFA in the action and follow-up.

Besides, ANEFA, as WP9 leader, will oversee the collection of different records of the event, such as the programme, agenda, minutes, signature list, pictures, video, etc.).

3.4.3.2 Invitation to scientific conferences and other events

Events organised by one or more Consortium Members

As required in *D9.1 Dissemination, communication, and exploitation plan*, in addition to the events defaulted defined in the GA, CM should promote the organisation of new ones where the project has a unique (exclusive event for DEQ) or shared (with other topics) presence.

In both cases, the invitation of policy makers, regulators and public bodies as speakers or attendees is a priority.

ANEFA is available to collaborate in the elaboration of the programme, in the selection of the policy makers, regulators and public bodies to be invited, the formulation of their invitations, the coordination of their responses, and to provide dissemination and communication materials.

Once the event has taken place, the person in charge will send to ANEFA, as WP9 leader, the previously listed records of the event.

Events not organised by Consortium Members

As required in *D9.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan*, CM must identify conferences and other events promoted by third organisations, that are relevant to DEQ, and participate and/or collaborate in them. *D9.1 Annex XII* includes a preliminary list of identified events, fairs, and workshops with a proposed Consortium Member in charge of the participation.

These events could be an excellent occasion to present the project to policy makers, regulators and public bodies already invited by the organisers or suggest to the latter the presence of new ones of interest to us.

In this case, the Consortium Member participating will oversee the collection of the different records of the event. They also must fill out the form for events, congresses, fairs, and workshops in *D9.1 Annex XIII*.

4 KPIs

To support and monitor the communication with policy makers and public bodies plan, it is necessary to collect **evidence** of the implementation as a basis for **KPIs** calculation.

4.1 Evidence

When interacting with policy makers and public bodies, it is not always possible to have physical verifiable evidence of all the activities. Nevertheless, for DEQ the following objective evidence will be considered:

E.1] Contacts list used for the distribution of:

- **Promotional material** (brochures leaflets, posters, or infographics).
- **Publications** (press releases, online newsletter, dissemination and communication articles in journals and magazines, scientific publications, public deliverables, joint public-private publications, letters, specific reports, or executive summaries).
- **Invitations** to public events.

E.2] Emails and letters asking for meetings or inviting to events or accompanying communication materials with policy makers and public bodies when existing.

E.3] Agendas or programs of the meetings with policy makers and public bodies when existing.

E.4] Pictures or videos of the meetings with policy makers and public bodies when existing.

E.5] Minutes or written reports of the meetings with policy makers and public bodies when existing.

E.6] Attendance/signature of the meetings with policy makers and public bodies when existing.

E.7] Surveys or reports completed by policy makers and public bodies when applicable.

E.8] Verbal report of the meeting or the communication action.

E.9] Communication materials produced for interactions with policy makers.

E.10] Evaluable results and outcomes from interactions with policy makers.

4.2 KPIs

For the management and evaluation of the policy makers' and public bodies' communication impact, the following simple KPIs are proposed.

A: Number of policy makers and public bodies **identified, listed, and included in the database**. (Evidence: E1]).

B: Number of policy makers and public bodies **invited to meetings** (individual or collective). (Evidence: E1] and/or E2]).

C: Number of meetings (individual or collective) with policy makers and public bodies. (Evidence: E3] and/or E4] and/or E5] and/or E6] and/or E8]).

D: Number of policy makers and public bodies **contacted in meetings** (individual or collective). (Evidence: E3] and/or E4] and/or E5] and/or E6] and/or E8]).

E: Number of different policy makers and public bodies **contacted with communication materials**. (Evidence: E1] and/or E2] and/or E9]).

F: Total number of contacts to policy makers and public bodies with communication materials (as each recipient of communication materials may receive several consignments during the project, each time a recipient receives them is counted here. (Evidence: E1] and/or E2] and/or E9]).

G: Percentage of identified policy makers and public bodies (A) participating in **activities of the project**, including workshops as speakers or participants. (Evidence: E3] and/or E4] and/or E5] and/or E6] and/or E8]).

H: Simplified qualitative external evaluation of the communication with policy makers and public bodies plan by a sample of members of the IAB and of supporting organisations, where each of the following qualitative parameters will be assessed (ranked from 1, very poor to 10 excellent) (Evidence: E7] and/or E5]):

- Adequacy of the list of policy makers and public bodies.
- Adequacy of the objectives of the communication strategy with policy makers and public bodies.
- Adequacy of communication materials used.
- Adequacy of the actions carried out.
- Degree of implementation of the communication plan with policy makers and public bodies.
- Overall quality of the communication plan with policy makers and public bodies.
- Overall impact of the communication plan with policy makers and public bodies.

I: Objectively evaluable results and outcomes of the communication with policy makers and public bodies plan. When measurable, the concrete results of the communication with policy makers and public bodies will be collected and will be assessed. (Evidence: E10]).

The KPIs evolution will be analysed on a periodic basis temporarily aligned with the global working plan of the project. And in addition to that, they will be a part of **D7.8** and **D7.9**.

5 Management control timetable

A table to manage, organise and prioritise the communications with policy makers and public bodies plan has been prepared and is permanently updated along the 48 months of the project.

The format of this table is available in Annex IV.

The fields of information in the table are:

- No. of the action
- Date of the action (Day/Month /Year)
- Place of the action (name of the city and Country)
- Name of the institution (policy maker or public body)
- Type of institution (please select from a menu)
- Geographical area of competence (please select from a menu)
- Level of competence (please select from a menu)
- Position of the policy maker (please select from a menu)
- Type of communication action (please select from a menu)
- Main objective of the communication (please select from a menu)
- Communication materials (please select from a menu)
- DEQ coordinator (please select from a menu)
- DEQ partners in the action (please select from a menu). No and percentage.

The follow-up of this plan is closely linked with the management of the dissemination and communication plan and with the clustering plan.

6 Conclusions

This deliverable states how to communicate the topics of the DIGIECOQUARRY project with policy makers and public bodies. It defines the work procedure to meet DIGIECOQUARRY's goals set for this topic.

This deliverable is closely linked to previously published **D7.6**. Both documents must be used together by all Consortium Members to ensure the correct execution of the plan and the fulfilment of the objectives.

D7.8 and **D7.9 Evaluation report for communications with policy makers** will complement this deliverable in project months 36 and 48.

This deliverable includes the description of the structure of the deliverable as well as its scope, its relation to other tasks, activities and deliverables, and the procedures and plans for communication with policy makers.

Also, the different objectives of communication with policy makers and public bodies relate to the plan.

This deliverable defines more precisely than **D7.6** the partners' requirements and roles in the communication with policy makers and public bodies plan according to the different categories of policy makers, regulators and public bodies at international, EU, national, regional, and local levels.

The reference to dissemination and communication materials and tools is made to WP9 materials.

The deliverable describes the timeline of the plan, as well as the type of evidence and KPI to guarantee proper monitoring.

7 References

The following references have been used for the preparation of this deliverable:

- EU Horizon 2020 call.
- DIGIECOQUARRY Grant Agreement number 101003750.
- DIGIECOQUARRY Consortium Agreement.

WP7

- D7.6 Requirements for communication with policy makers and public bodies.

WP8

- D8.1 Clustering plan.
- D8.2 Protocols to cooperate with RMIS and EURMKB.

WP9

- D9.1 Dissemination, communication, and exploitation plan.
- D9.2 DIGIECOQUARRY's website.
- D9.3 Dissemination and communication materials.
- D9.4 Report on communication and dissemination activities

WP10

- D10.3 Risk management and contingency plan.

8 Annex I. Consortium Members preassigned to policy makers

As an initial reference, the CM preassigned to policy makers are listed below.

Name	Area of influence	Type of organisation	Link with the project	Consortium Member
Ministry of Mines and Energy	Colombia	Public Administrations and governments	Supporter	ASOGRAVAS
United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP)	Worldwide	International governance organisations	None	ANEFA
Federación Iberoamericana de Productores de Áridos (FIPA)	Ibero-America	Entrepreneurs Organisation	Supporter	ANEFA and ASOGRAVAS
Global Aggregates Information Network (GAIN)	Worldwide		Member of the IAB	ANEFA and ASOGRAVAS
BIRDLIFE International	Worldwide	Environmental NGO	Supporter	ANEFA
International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)	Worldwide		Member of the IAB	ANEFA
Heidelberg Cement Group	Worldwide	Corporate aggregates companies	Member of the IAB	ANEFA
CEMEX	Worldwide		Member of the IAB	ANEFA

TABLE A.I.2. EU-LEVEL POLICY MAKERS, REGULATORS AND PUBLIC BODIES

Name	Area of influence	Type of organisation	Link with the project	Consortium Member
European Parliament	EU	Parliament and other legislative and representative bodies	None	ANEFA
Committee of Regions	EU		None	ANEFA and DGASTUR
European Commission	EU	Public Administrations and governments	None	ANEFA
Council	EU		None	ANEFA
European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (EU-OSHA)	EU		Member of the IAB	ANEFA
European Environment Agency (EEA)	EU		Supporter	ANEFA
CEN and CENELEC	EU	Standardisation bodies	None	ANEFA
Geological Surveys of Europe (EuroGeoSurveys)	EU	Thinktanks	Member of the IAB	ANEFA
EIT Raw Materials	EU		None	ANEFA
European Raw Materials Alliance (ERMA)	EU		None	ANEFA
European Aggregates Association (UEPG)	EU	Entrepreneurs Organisations, ICT industry, Construction sector and other clients	Member of the IAB	ANEFA
Committee for European Construction Equipment (CECE)	EU		Supporter	ANEFA
EuroGypsum	EU		Supporter	ANEFA
European Asphalt Pavement Association (EAPA)	EU		Supporter	ANEFA
European Cement Association (CEMBUREAU)	EU		Supporter	ANEFA
EUROMINES	EU		Supporter (by ENSQM)	ANEFA
IMA Europe	EU		Supporter (by ENSQM)	ANEFA
Business Europe	EU		None	ANEFA
Non-Energy Extractive Industry Panel (NEEIP)	EU		None	ANEFA
Construction Products Europe (CPE)	EU		None	ANEFA
European Network for Sustainable Quarrying and Mining (ENSQM)	EU	Environmental Network	Supporter	ANEFA
Aggregates Business Europe (AGGB)	EU	Medias	Member of the IAB	ANEFA
IndustriAll	EU	Trade Unions	None	ANEFA
European Technology Platform on Sustainable Mineral Resources (ETP SMR)	EU	Other lobbyist entities	None	ANEFA

TABLE A.I.3. EU NATIONAL POLICY MAKERS, REGULATORS AND PUBLIC BODIES

Name	Area of influence	Type of organisation	Link with the project	Consortium Member
Spanish Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge	Spain	Public Administrations and governments	Supporter	ANEFA
Ministry of Mines and Energy	Colombia		Supporter	ASOGRAVAS
Instituto Geológico y Minero de España (IGME)	Spain		Supporter	ANEFA
Other Ministries related with the extractive industry and with environmental issues	All EU countries + Colombia + South Africa		None	ALL EU PARTNERS
Other Geological Surveys			Supporter (by EGS)	ALL PARTNERS
H&S national Bodies			None	ALL PARTNERS
Environmental national bodies			None	ALL PARTNERS
Standardisation national bodies			Standardisation bodies	None
Universities		Accademia	None	ALL PARTNERS
AGH University of Science and Technology – Mining and Geoengineering Faculty	Poland	Academia	Supporter	ANEFA
Spanish Concrete Technical Platform (PTEH)	Spain	Thinktanks	None	ANEFA
Other National Bodies related with the Aggregates Industry	All EU countries + Colombia + South Africa	Other	None	ALL PARTNERS
Associação Nacional da Industria Extractiva e Transformadora (ANIET)	Portugal	Entrepreneurs Organisations	Supporter	CIMPOR
Associazione Nazionale Estrattori Produttori Lapidei ed Affini (ANEPLA)	Italy		Supporter	HOLCIM
Confederación Española de Asociaciones de Fabricantes de Productos de Construcción (CEPCO)	Spain		Supporter	ANEFA
Asociación Nacional Española de Fabricantes de Hormigón Preparado (ANEFHOP)	Spain		None	ANEFA
FEDIEX	Belgium		Supporter (by UEPG)	ANEFA
Mineral Products Association (MPA)	UK		Supporter (by UEPG)	ANEFA
Spanish Confederation of Business Organisations (CEOE)	Spain		None	ANEFA
Spanish Confederation of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (CEPYME)	Spain		None	ANEFA
Confederación Española de Industrias Extractivas de Rocas y Minerales Industriales (COMINROC)	Spain		Supporter	ANEFA
Confederación Española de las Industrias de las Materias Primas Minerales (PRIMIGEA)	Spain		Supporter	ANEFA
Confederación Nacional de Empresarios de la Minería y Metalurgia (CONFEDEM)	Spain	Supporter	ANEFA	

Name	Area of influence	Type of organisation	Link with the project	Consortium Member
Fachverband der Stein- und keramischen Industrie Österreich (FVSK)	Austria	Entrepreneurs Organisations	Supporter	MUL
Gremi d'Àrids de Catalunya	Spain		Supporter	ANEFA
Spanish Aggregates Federation (FdA)	Spain		Supporter	ANEFA
National Aggregates Associations	All EU countries + Colombia + South Africa		Supporter (by UEPG)	ALL PARTNERS
Union Nationale des Producteurs de Granulats (UNPG)	France		Supporter	VICAT
Organisations from the construction sector and other client industries	All EU countries + Colombia + South Africa		None	ALL PARTNERS
Fundación Tormes – E.B.	Spain	Environmental NGO	Supporter	ANEFA
Environmental NGOs	All EU countries + Colombia + South Africa		None	ALL PARTNERS
Centro Tecnológico del Mármol, Piedra y Materiales	Spain	Technological Centre	Supporter	ANEFA
Laboratorio Oficial Madariaga (LOM)	Spain		Supporter	ANEFA
Citizens and civil society organisations	All EU countries + Colombia + South Africa	Civil society	None	ALL PARTNERS
Media and journalists	All EU countries + Colombia + South Africa		None	ALL PARTNERS

TABLE A.I.4. REGIONAL AND LOCAL POLICY MAKERS, REGULATORS AND PUBLIC BODIES

Name	Area of influence	Type of organisation	Link with the project	Consortium Member
Dirección General de Industria, Energía y Minas de la Comunidad de Madrid	Spain	Public Administrations, governments and public bodies	Supporter	ANEFA
Other regional Administrations related with the extractive industry	All regions		None	ALL PARTNERS
Other regional public bodies related with the extractive industry	All regions		None	ALL PARTNERS
Citizens and civil society organisations	All EU countries + Colombia + South Africa	Civil society	None	ALL PARTNERS
Media and journalists	All EU countries + Colombia + South Africa		None	ALL PARTNERS

9 Annex II. Consortium Members preassigned to the International Advisory Board

Name of the member	Area of influence	Type of organisation	Added value	Link with other policy makers and public bodies	Partner in charge of the collaboration
Aggregates Business Europe (AGGB)	EU	Media company	Can advise on the content of the messages to be delivered to policy makers	Other media	ANEFA
European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (EU-OSHA)	EU	European Official Agency Policy maker	EU-OSHA has strong relationships with all its partners — the European Commission, the national focal points, the social partners, the campaign partners, and its stakeholders	EU-OSHA has a national focal point in each Member State. They are typically the competent national authority for safety and health at work	ANEFA
European Aggregates Association (UEPG)	EU	Entrepreneurs Organisation Policy maker	Excellent contacts with all EU relevant policy makers	26 UEPG Member associations NEEIP associations Other European associations related with aggregates industry	ANEFA
Federal Association of Mineral Raw Materials E.V. (MIRO)	Germany	Entrepreneurs Organisation Policy maker	Excellent contacts with all German relevant policy makers	Other German associations related with aggregates industry	ANEFA
Geological Surveys of Europe (EuroGeoSurveys)	EU	Policy maker	EuroGeoSurveys members, the National Geological Surveys, are public sector institutions carrying out operations and research in the field of geosciences	38 National Geological Surveys and some regional Surveys in Europe	ANEFA UPM MUL
Global Aggregates Information Network (GAIN)	Worldwide	Entrepreneurs Organisation Policy maker	Excellent contacts with Worldwide Aggregates Associations	22 UEPG Member associations	ANEFA
International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)	Worldwide	Environmental NGO Policy maker	Union composed of both government and civil society organisations	1,400 member organisations	ANEFA
Heidelberg Cement Group	Worldwide	Aggregates, Cement, Readymix concrete and Asphalt producer company	3,000 sites in 50 countries	Local and regional policy makers	ANEFA
CEMEX	Worldwide	Aggregates, Cement, Readymix concrete and Asphalt producer company	296 aggregates sites in 22 countries	Local and regional policy makers	ANEFA
DST (new)	Portugal	Aggregates, Readymix concrete and Asphalt producer company	4 aggregates sites	Local and regional policy makers	ANEFA and CIMPOR

Name of the member	Area of influence	Type of organisation	Added value	Link with other policy makers and public bodies	Partner in charge of the collaboration
Exxia (new)	France	Software for quality management company	Potential synergies with the project	UNPG, ANEFA and other organisations from client sectors	ANEFA

10Annex III. Consortium Members preassigned to organisations supporting DIGIECOQUARRY

ORGANISATIONS SUPPORTING DIGIECOQUARRY		
Name and Area of influence	Type of organisation	Partner in charge of the collaboration
European Environment Agency (EU-Denmark)	Public Administrations	ANEFA
Spanish Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge (Spain)		ANEFA
Ministry of Mines and Energy (Colombia)		ASOGRAVAS
Instituto Geológico y Minero de España (IGME) (Spain)	Academia	ANEFA
AGH University of Science and Technology – Mining and Geoengineering Faculty (Poland)		ANEFA
Associação Nacional da Industria Extractiva e Transformadora (ANIET) (Portugal)	Entrepreneurs Organisation	CIMPOR
Associazione Nazionale Estrattori Produttori Lapidei ed Affini (ANEPLA) (Italy)		HOLCIM
Confederación Española de Asociaciones de Fabricantes de Productos de Construcción (CEPCO) (Spain)		ANEFA
Confederación Española de Industrias Extractivas de Rocas y Minerales Industriales (COMINROC) (Spain)		ANEFA
Confederación Española de las Industrias de las Materias Primas Minerales (PRIMIGEA) (Spain)		ANEFA
Confederación Nacional de Empresarios de la Minería y Metalurgia (CONFEDEM) (Spain)		ANEFA
Committee for European Construction Equipment (CECE) (EU-Brussels)		ANEFA
Dirección General de Industria, Energía y Minas de la Comunidad de Madrid (Spain)		ANEFA
EuroGypsum (EU-Brussels)		ANEFA
European Asphalt Pavement Association (EAPA) (EU-Brussels)		ANEFA
European Cement Association (CEMBUREAU) (EU-Brussels)		ANEFA
Fachverband der Stein- und keramischen Industrie Österreich (FVSK) (Austria)		ANEFA
Federación Iberoamericana de Productores de Áridos (FIPA) (Ibero-América)		ANEFA and ASOGRAVAS
Gremi d'Àrids de Catalunya (Spain)		ANEFA
Spanish Aggregates Federation (FdA) (Spain)		ANEFA
Union Nationale des Producteurs de Granulats (UNPG) (France)		VICAT
BIRDLIFE International (EU-Brussels)		Environmental NGO
Fundación Tormes – E.B. (Spain)	Environmental NGO	ANEFA
European Network for Sustainable Quarrying and Mining (EU-Brussels)	Environmental Network	ANEFA
Centro Tecnológico del Mármol, Piedra y Materiales (Spain)	Technological Centre	ANEFA
Laboratorio Oficial Madariaga (LOM) (Spain)	Technological Centre	ANEFA

